

The idiolectal information in long character n-grams: An experiment using paraphrasing.

Sadie Barlow and Dr Andrea Nini

Character N-grams

Characte	haracter	aracter_	racter_N
acter_N-	cter_N-g	ter_N-gr	er_N-gra
r_N-gram	_N-grams		

Authorship Attribution

N-gram Tracing

Q

A

B

N-gram Tracing

A

B

N-gram Tracing

A

B

N-gram Tracing

A

B

$$\text{Overlap Coefficient} = \frac{|A \cap B|}{\min(|A|, |B|)}$$

N-gram Tracing

$$\text{Overlap Coefficient} = \frac{|A \cap B|}{\min(|A|, |B|)}$$

N-gram Tracing

Overlap Coefficient = $\frac{|A \cap B|}{\min(|A|, |B|)}$

4/5 = 80%

$$\text{Jaccard Coefficient} = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}$$

$$\text{Jaccard Coefficient} = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} = 21\%$$

“They are starting to become friends.”

“It’s proving to be a challenge.”

“I’m going to be late.”

ing to be

“They’re turning out to be good friends”

“I’m going to be late.”

“It’s turning out to be a challenge”

turning out to be

A

B

Research Question

- Do different individuals consistently use different sets of n-grams to encode a particular meaning as predicted by cognitive linguistic theories or are n-grams successful because they capture information that is only correlated to authorship (e.g. topic)?

18 Participants

- 19-22 years old
- Undergraduate student
- Native speaker of British English

Write a detailed summary of 'Kevin' in your own words.

Kevin

Kevin had recently started high school and his parents were very proud of him. 'We never got that opportunity,' Kevin's mother told him. 'Your father was certainly bright enough to go to high school and maybe he could even have been a teacher instead of working in a shop.' When Kevin had homework, his father was very interested and sometimes attempted the exercises from the textbooks on his own before he went to bed. After a while he even felt confident enough to try to help his son.

One night his father was getting ready to go out and stood shaving in the bathroom. Kevin came into the tiny room, hoping to get some help with the Latin sentences he had to translate. 'I don't have time to help you work it out for yourself, so I'll tell you the answers just this one time,' he said. Kevin held his pencil poised and wrote the answers into his notebook as his father confidently called them out with great speed. As he rushed out of the front door, his father shouted up the stairs. 'Don't ever ask me to do that again. You have to learn to do it without my help.'

The next morning, Kevin made his way to his Latin class. Of all the teachers in the school, the Latin teacher, Mr Waldo, was the one who commanded the most respect. Students seeing him walk along the corridor dropped their voices until he was out of earshot. 'Right, homework.' The atmosphere was tense as Mr Waldo looked from one student to another. 'We'll begin with you Kevin.' Kevin rose to his feet, his fingers trembling under the book. He read out his first sentence and looked up at Mr Waldo whose face was expressionless. Kevin went slowly through the whole exercise and stopped, waiting anxiously for a comment from the teacher. It was a long time before he spoke. 'Every one of them is wrong,' he said.

18 Participants

- 19-22 years old
- Undergraduate student
- Native speaker of British English

Write a detailed summary of 'Kevin' in your own words.

At least 30 days

Write a detailed summary of 'Kevin' in your own words.

Jaccard Coefficient = $\frac{3}{14} = 21\%$

**Intra-author
variation**

Differences within
the same author

**Inter-author
variation**

Differences between
two authors

Similarity Score Distribution

Figure 1: Boxplot to show the similarity between texts based on 7-grams, depending on whether they were written by the same person

$p < 0.001$

Frequency of Consistent 7-grams

Figure 1: Bar chart to show the distribution of 7-grams that were used consistently by one or more author

Common 7-grams

- “_answer”

Proportion of Consistent 7-grams Used in the Stimulus

Figure 2: Bar chart to show the distribution of 7-grams that were used consistently by one or more author and the proportion of these used in the stimulus

7-grams used consistently by 9 authors

“_him_th”	“_to_hel”	“his_ans”	“is_fath”	”the_nex”
“_his_an”	“e_next_”	“his_fat”	“is_pare”	“to_help”
“_his_fa”	“each_”	“his_par”	“s answe”	
“_the_ne”	“he_next”	“is_answ”	“school”	

7-grams used consistently by 9 authors

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Unique 7-grams

Table 2: Table containing randomly sampled unique 7-grams of three authors

Author	7-grams
1	“_is_a_y”, “oy_who_”, “_to_do.”
2	“cher_an”, “ous_and”, “us_and_“
3	“_is_cal”, “n_learn”, “o_to_re”

Authorship Attribution

Table 3: Table containing the rank (based on similarity) of the other text written by the same author

	7-grams
Median Rank	1
% ranked 1	75%
% ranked top 3	94.44%

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Sadie Barlow - sadie.barlow@postgrad.manchester.ac.uk

Andrea Nini - andrea.nini@manchester.ac.uk